

Impact of Processing Approach on SNR Performance for Passive Bistatic Noise Radar

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Abstract—In passive bistatic noise radar, cross-correlation is a popular processing choice for range compression of received signals. However, when using cross-correlation, the noise floor is dependent upon the characteristics of the clutter in the scene. For similar computational requirements, least-mean-square (LMS) processing can yield signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) performance which is independent of the clutter characteristics, making it a superior choice relative to cross-correlation. The superior SNR performance of LMS relative to cross-correlation may be even more striking when the transmitted noise waveform is not spectrally uniform. This paper will study the results achieved in a zero-Doppler range profile containing a single point scatterer and multiple point scatterers when cross-correlation, whitened cross-correlation, and LMS processing are used with a transmitted waveform whose spectrum is flat (white noise) and notched (colored noise).

I. INTRODUCTION

Passive bistatic noise radar can be an attractive choice relative to monostatic radar because it can provide a low probability of intercept (LPI), immunity to jamming and interference, the ability to operate outside of traditional radar bands, and reduced cost. Common radar waveforms such as linear frequency modulation (LFM), which perform well in monostatic radar, are poorly suited for bistatic radar due to mutual interference and lack of adaptability in terms of range-Doppler ambiguity and multi-function operability [1]. The benefits of noise waveforms versus classic radar waveforms such as LFM are discussed in [2]. Noise waveforms, with their thumbtack ambiguity functions, are actively being studied for use in passive bistatic radar. Since many digital waveforms are specifically randomized to make their spectra approximately white, noise-like waveforms may be readily available for opportunistic use by passive radar receivers.

The use of noise waveforms in radar is not new. The concept of noise radar with coherent reception of radar returns has been around since the 1950s [3].

By using a direct path receive antenna to record the transmitted noise waveform (the reference signal), and a separate receive antenna to record radar echoes (the received signal), the reference signal may be used to process the received signal. Cross-correlation has been used as a processing technique when a random waveform is used on transmit since the earliest days of noise radar [3]. Cross-correlation may be used to

compress pseudo-pulses (blocks of contiguous samples of the received signal), achieving range resolution. Each compressed pseudo-pulse is a superposition of shifted replicas of the cross-correlation of the reference signal with the received signal. The compression is performed in software, and is demanding in terms of computational and memory requirements [1].

The noise background includes thermal noise, plus noise due to hardware limitations (finite precision), and noise due to the particular processing technique used. When cross-correlation is performed, the intrinsic expected SNR for each scatterer (i.e. the expected SNR for each scatterer when the only noise present is due to the processing technique) has been shown in [1] to degrade linearly as the number of scatterers (with equal power received from each) in the scene increases, even though the thermal noise level has not changed, because cross-correlation sidelobes from other scatterers, behaving statistically like white noise, add with thermal noise, increasing the noise background.

Adding a whitening filter after cross-correlation yields the least-squares (LS) algorithm, which, because it involves a matrix inversion, is deemed to be too computationally costly to be used in practice at the present time, though results achieved by using LS are included in this paper.

As shown in [4], the LMS [5] algorithm may also be used for range profile estimation in noise radar pseudo-pulse compression. This is accomplished by treating the complex-valued range profile as an unknown channel, modeled by a finite impulse response (FIR) filter [1]. The processor within the receiver treats the illuminated scene as a linear system with unknown coefficients, which filters the transmitted signal. Given access to the transmitted waveform and the digitized backscattered signal, the receiver adaptively estimates the unknown filter coefficients, using the same processing architecture as a wireless channel identifier, and continues to update the filter coefficient values as the transmitter and receiver traverse their flight paths. The adapted filters correspond to range profiles of the illuminated scene [6].

The LMS algorithm is known to converge to the LS solution in the mean [7]. It is shown in [1] that the intrinsic expected SNR for each scatterer when LMS processing is performed is independent of the number of scatterers. This characteristic may be useful when both strong and weak scatterers are

present, to avoid masking of weaker radar returns by stronger ones. Equations for expected SNR when cross-correlation processing and conventional LMS processing are employed are given in [1], while [8] presents equations for expected SNR when cross-correlation and block LMS processing are considered. Only conventional (not block) LMS will be considered in this paper.

Much of the literature assumes that the transmitted noise waveform is white (i.e. it has a uniform power spectral density, meaning that its spectrum is flat) over a finite bandwidth. However, illuminators of opportunity that employ analog modulation of their transmitted waveforms (such as FM broadcast transmitters) may emit waveforms which are not white. When the transmitted waveform's spectrum is colored (i.e. not having a uniform power spectral density), the cross-correlation process is likely to produce sidelobes that are unacceptably high. Meanwhile, LMS may produce sidelobes that are more acceptable. This paper will study the results obtained from cross-correlation, from the LMS algorithm with different values of the step-size parameter μ used in the tap-weight vector (range profile) update equation, and from LS, as the transmitted waveform becomes more spectrally non-uniform.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the bistatic noise radar model used in this analysis. Section III discusses processing architectures. Section IV presents simulation results when the transmitted noise waveform has a flat spectrum, and when the transmitted noise waveform has a spectral notch. Three cases are investigated: no spectral notch (i.e. a flat spectrum) on transmit, a "medium-sized" spectral notch on transmit, and a "wide" spectral notch on transmit, with one scatterer and with eight scatterers in the scene in each case. Section V presents conclusions.

The notation used in this paper is as follows. Column vectors are denoted by underlined lower-case letters (e.g., \underline{x}). The conjugate transpose of a vector or matrix is denoted by $(\cdot)^H$ (e.g., \underline{x}^H, X^H), and complex conjugation is denoted by $(\cdot)^*$ (e.g., \underline{x}^*).

II. BISTATIC NOISE RADAR MODEL

Figure 1 provides a top view of a bistatic data collection geometry, which is shown modeled in Matlab by Figure 5 in Section IV where simulation results are presented. Figure 5 illustrates the simple, notional scenario which was modeled and simulated, with an airborne transmit platform (red dot) from whence the transmitted noise waveform originates and propagates forth, an airborne receive radar platform (blue dot) which has one antenna pointed at the transmit platform to record the transmitted (reference) waveform and another antenna pointed at the scene containing the scatterers to act as a radar receive antenna, and eight point scatterers (green dots) on the ground (a flat earth geometry has been used), with one of the scatterers at scene center (0,0,0) and the other scatterers lying along the x-axis with the y and z coordinates of all eight scatterers set equal to zero. The transmit and receive platforms, and the eight scatterers, have all been assigned a velocity of

zero, because this paper focuses on the effect that a notch in the transmitted waveform will have on zero-Doppler range profiles. For half of the cases considered in this paper, only the scatterer at scene center (0,0,0) remains in the scene (the other seven have been removed), while for the other half of the cases, all eight scatterers are in the scene. This affords us an opportunity to compare algorithm performance (particularly in regard to sidelobe level) as a spectral notch appears and grows wider when only one scatterer is in the scene, and when multiple scatterers are in the scene.

Fig. 1. Top view of a bistatic data collection geometry. The x-y plane is the ground plane. [4].

III. PROCESSING ARCHITECTURES

We can treat the problem of estimating the range profile by thinking of the illuminated scene as a system for which we want to perform channel identification to form an estimate of the filter coefficients needed to convert the reference waveform into the received waveform. The filter has a number of taps, which correspond to range bins, and the filter coefficients are the tap weights which convert the tap-input vector (the reference waveform) into the received (desired) signal. The vector of these tap weights corresponds to the range profile.

A. Simple Cross-Correlation

Figure 2 shows a block diagram of the cross-correlation processing architecture.

If the received and reference signals, $d(n)$ and $u(n)$, are segmented into pseudo-pulses of Q samples, the estimated reflectivity at the p th range gate is computed via cross-correlation as [4]

$$\hat{h}_q(p) = \sum_{n=q}^{q+Q} u(n-p)d^*(n) \quad (1)$$

where q denotes the sample at the beginning of a pseudo-pulse of Q samples.

The above can be written in a form used to update the tap-weight (range profile) vector on a sample-by-sample basis as

$$\hat{h}(n+1) = \hat{h}(n) + \underline{u}(n)d^*(n) \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{h}(n)$ is the previous estimate of the range profile, $\underline{u}(n)$ is the transmitted (reference) waveform, and $d^*(n)$ is the conjugate of the desired (received) waveform.

Fig. 2. Noise radar receiver-correlator architecture (cross-correlation processing) [4].

B. Simple Cross-Correlation With Whitening

Figure 3 shows a block diagram of the processing architecture for simple cross-correlation followed by whitening.

The intrinsic performance of cross-correlation can be improved by computing an estimate of the autocorrelation function of the tap-input vector (i.e. the reference signal), taking its inverse, and multiplying the output of the cross-correlator by the inverse of the tap-input vector's autocorrelation matrix to statistically "whiten" the correlator's output. The output of the whitening operation is $\hat{R}_u^{-1}\hat{h}_q$, which is the well-known least-squares solution [4], where \hat{R}_u is the sample estimate of the autocorrelation matrix of the transmitted (reference) waveform.

The above can be written in the form used to update the tap-weight (range profile) vector on a sample-by-sample basis as

$$\hat{h}(n+1) = \hat{h}(n) + \underline{u}(n)d^*(n) \quad (3)$$

which is the same as Equation (2). After performing the above operation for all Q samples in the pseudo-pulse, perform the following multiplication

$$\hat{h}(Q) = \hat{R}_u^{-1}\hat{h}(Q) \quad (4)$$

Note the similarity to the Wiener filter, which defines the minimum mean-squared error [6].

$$\underline{w}_* = R_u^{-1}\underline{\rho}_{ud} \quad (5)$$

where \underline{w}_* is the optimum value of \underline{w} (here, \underline{w}_* represents \hat{h} , which is the true range profile), $R_u = E\{\underline{u}(n)\underline{u}^H(n)\}$, which is the true autocorrelation of the tap-input vector (reference waveform) $\underline{u}(n)$, and $\underline{\rho}_{ud} = E\{\underline{u}(n)d^*(n)\}$, which is the true cross-correlation of the tap-input vector (reference waveform) $\underline{u}(n)$ and the conjugate of the desired (received) signal $d(n)$.

Fig. 3. Noise radar receiver-correlator architecture with a whitening filter added after correlation (LS processing) [4].

C. Stochastic Implementation Of Gradient Descent

Figure 4 shows a block diagram of the adaptive channel ID processing architecture, which is implemented here via LMS.

Using conventional LMS, the tap-weight vector (range profile) estimate at the output of iteration $n+1$ is $\hat{h}(n+1)$, which can be computed as

$$\begin{aligned} e(n) &= d(n) - \hat{h}^H(n)\underline{u}(n) \\ \hat{h}(n+1) &= \hat{h}(n) + \mu\underline{u}(n)e^*(n) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $e(n)$ is an error signal forced to zero by the LMS algorithm, $d(n)$ is the desired (received) signal, $\underline{u}(n)$ is the tap-input vector (reference waveform), and μ is a step-size. Equation (6) converges to the Wiener solution (Equation (5)) in the mean [6]. The smaller the step-size μ , the smaller the mean-squared error, but the longer it will take for the LMS algorithm to converge. In a dynamic environment, the true range profile will change as a function of time, and the step-size μ must be large enough to keep up with changes so that the estimated range profile is kept accurate over time. However, too large a step-size will cause the LMS algorithm to become unstable.

Fig. 4. Adaptive noise radar receiver architecture (LMS processing) [4].

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 5 illustrates the scenario geometry of Figure 1 modeled in Matlab, while Table I lists the parameters (not necessarily realistic) used to generate the simulated results. The transmit and receive platform velocities have been set to zero, as have the velocities of all the scatterers, and perfect knowledge of the transmitted noise (or noise-like) waveform is assumed in the receiver. This paper focuses solely on computing estimated range profiles at zero-Doppler, using various algorithms. Other papers in the literature, such as [9], [10], and [11], consider the entire range-Doppler plane (not just the zero-Doppler range profile), and study the cancellation

TABLE I
PARAMETERS USED IN THE SIMULATION

Parameter	Value
Tx Velocity	0.0 m/s
Rx Velocity	0.0 m/s
Number of Scatterers	1, 8
Scatterer Velocities	0.0 m/s
Each Scatterer's Avg Power at Radar Rx	1
Avg Power of Tx Waveform	1
Avg Rx Thermal Noise Power	1
Number of Range Bins	50
Center Frequency	10.0 GHz
Bandwidth of Tx Waveform	20.0 MHz
Sampling Rate	20.0 MHz
Approx Step-Sizes μ Used in LMS	0.004, 0.0067, 0.0093, 0.012
Number of Monte Carlo Realizations	1000

of zero-Doppler clutter, the direct path signal, and multipath to better reveal moving targets, and the interested reader is referred to those papers.

Fig. 5. Scenario geometry modeled in Matlab.

Note in Table I that the sampling rate has been set equal to the transmitted waveform's bandwidth. Because the transmitted waveform is modeled as a sequence of complex random samples, the minimum sampling rate required by Nyquist to avoid aliasing is achieved and no aliasing will occur.

A. Case 1. The Transmitted Waveform's Spectrum is Flat - One Scatterer and Eight Scatterers

Figure 6 illustrates the white noise (flat spectrum) of the transmitted waveform in Case 1. The periodogram was computed for the transmitted noise waveform used in one of 1000 Monte Carlo realizations. The transmitted waveform is white Gaussian noise with variance (average power) shown in Table I. The transmitted noise waveform is independent of the receiver thermal noise.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 present the tap-weight vector estimates (range profile estimates) generated using the techniques considered in this paper, with one and with eight point scatterers in the scene and with the transmit waveform's spectrum as illustrated in the periodogram of Figure 6. The range profile

Fig. 6. Periodogram illustrating the white noise (flat spectrum) of the transmitted waveform for Case 1. The periodogram converges to the transmit spectrum in the mean value.

estimates shown have been averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo runs. Each range profile estimate plot has been normalized so that the peak of each is at 0 dB for ease of visual comparison of peak-to-sidelobe ratio between range profile estimates. This normalization of range profile estimates has been done for all of the range profile estimate plots in this paper. This peak-to-sidelobe ratio is referred to as "signal-to-noise ratio" (SNR) in this paper. Note that the range sidelobes for the range profile estimated by cross-correlation are roughly 6-7 dB higher in Figure 8 than in Figure 7. This is because when eight scatterers (with equal power received from each) are in the scene instead of just one, the average range sidelobe level estimated using cross-correlation is predicted to be approximately eight times as high due to the cross-correlation sidelobes acting statistically like white noise, adding with thermal noise. Note that the mean range side lobes using LMS with four different step-sizes are essentially unchanged between Figure 7 and Figure 8, showing in the simulation results that the expected SNR for each scatterer when LMS processing is employed is independent of the number of equal power scatterers.

Fig. 7. Range profile estimates (one scatterer in the scene) for the case of a white noise (flat spectrum) waveform being used on transmit, using simple cross-correlation processing (black), conventional LMS (solid red: step-size = 0.004, dashed red: step-size = 0.0067, dash-dot red: step-size = 0.0093, dot-dot red: step-size = 0.012), and LS (i.e. cross-correlation followed by a whitening filter) (blue).

Case 1 serves as a useful starting point in the analysis. Cases 2 and 3 filter out a portion of the transmitted waveform's

Fig. 8. Range profile estimates (eight scatterers in the scene) for the case of a white noise (flat spectrum) waveform being used on transmit, using simple cross-correlation processing (black), conventional LMS (solid red: step-size = 0.004, dashed red: step-size = 0.0067, dash-dot red: step-size = 0.0093, dot-dot red: step-size = 0.012), and LS (i.e. cross-correlation followed by a whitening filter) (blue).

spectrum to create a notch, to avoid transmitting in a certain frequency band. As the notch gets wider, the processing algorithms yield tap-weight vectors (range profile estimates) with smaller peak-to-sidelobe ratios and warping or “bowing” as a function of position along the range profile.

B. Case 2. The Transmitted Waveform’s Spectrum Contains a Medium-Sized Notch - One Scatterer and Eight Scatterers

In Case 2, a medium-sized notch (5% of the transmit waveform’s bandwidth) is carved in the transmit waveform’s spectrum. Figure 9 shows the periodogram of the transmitted waveform (for one of the 1000 Monte Carlo runs), and Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the range profile estimates which were generated using the transmit waveform whose periodogram is illustrated in Figure 9. The range profiles shown have been averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo runs.

Fig. 9. Periodogram illustrating the colored noise spectrum of the transmitted waveform for Case 2, containing a medium-sized notch (5% of the spectrum was notched out). The periodogram converges to the transmit spectrum in the mean value.

Notice the “bowing” of the sidelobe level for the range profile estimates generated using cross-correlation and LS in Figures 10 and 11, and notice that bowing is exhibited by LMS as well in Figure 11.

Fig. 10. Range profile estimates (one scatterer in the scene) for the case of a colored noise spectrum waveform, containing a medium-sized notch, being used on transmit, using simple cross-correlation processing (black), conventional LMS (solid red: step-size = 0.004, dashed red: step-size = 0.0067, dash-dot red: step-size = 0.0093, dot-dot red: step-size = 0.012), and LS (i.e. cross-correlation followed by a whitening filter) (blue).

Fig. 11. Range profile estimates (eight scatterers in the scene) for the case of a colored noise spectrum waveform, containing a medium-sized notch, being used on transmit, using simple cross-correlation processing (black), conventional LMS (solid red: step-size = 0.004, dashed red: step-size = 0.0067, dash-dot red: step-size = 0.0093, dot-dot red: step-size = 0.012), and LS (i.e. cross-correlation followed by a whitening filter) (blue).

C. Case 3. The Transmitted Waveform’s Spectrum Contains a Wide Notch - One Scatterer and Eight Scatterers

In Case 3, a wide notch (10% of the transmit waveform’s bandwidth) is carved in the transmit waveform’s spectrum. Figure 12 illustrates the periodogram of the transmitted waveform for one of 1000 Monte Carlo runs, and Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the range profile estimates which were generated using the transmit waveform whose periodogram is illustrated in Figure 12. The range profiles shown have been averaged over 1000 Monte Carlo runs.

Notice the “bowing” of the sidelobe level for the range profile estimates generated using cross-correlation and LS in Figures 13 and 14, and notice that bowing is showing for LMS as well in Figure 13, and is fully evident in Figure 14. LMS seems to be more robust than the other algorithms in resisting the introduction of bowing.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper studied the range profile estimates at zero Doppler obtained using cross-correlation, conventional LMS

Fig. 12. Periodogram illustrating the colored noise spectrum of the transmitted waveform for Case 3, containing a wide notch (10% of the spectrum was notched out). The periodogram converges to the transmit spectrum in the mean value.

Fig. 13. Range profile estimates (one scatterer in the scene) for the case of a colored noise spectrum waveform, containing a wide notch, being used on transmit, using simple cross-correlation processing (black), conventional LMS (solid red: step-size = 0.004, dashed red: step-size = 0.0067, dash-dot red: step-size = 0.0093, dot-dot red: step-size = 0.012), and LS (i.e. cross-correlation followed by a whitening filter) (blue).

Fig. 14. Range profile estimates (eight scatterers in the scene) for the case of a colored noise spectrum waveform, containing a wide notch, being used on transmit, using simple cross-correlation processing (black), conventional LMS (solid red: step-size = 0.004, dashed red: step-size = 0.0067, dash-dot red: step-size = 0.0093, dot-dot red: step-size = 0.012), and LS (i.e. cross-correlation followed by a whitening filter) (blue).

with four different step-sizes used in the range profile update equation, and LS, when the transmitted waveform consisted of white noise (a flat spectrum) and when the transmitted waveform's spectrum became progressively more non-uniform (notched). All algorithms performed well when the transmitted waveform was white noise, with LS performing the best. Cross-correlation processing performed almost as well as LS processing, followed by LMS processing, with the LMS step-size used in the tap-weight vector (range profile) update equation influencing the overall sidelobe level yielded by LMS. When eight scatterers were in the scene, instead of just one scatterer, the sidelobes using cross-correlation increased roughly in proportion to the increase in the number of equal power scatterers in the scene, due to the noise contributions made by the multiple scatterers to the average sidelobe level in the range profile estimate produced by cross-correlation. Performance for all algorithms was worse when the transmitted waveform contained a notch. Conventional LMS generally exhibited sidelobe control that was not influenced by an increase in the number of scatterers or by a small notch in the spectrum. When a spectral notch was present, LS degraded the most as the spectral notch got wide. Lastly, since the conventional LMS algorithm used in adaptive noise radar processing is nearly identical in implementation to the algorithms used in wireless channel ID, leveraging commercial wireless channel ID technology may allow adaptive noise radar receiver processors which employ conventional LMS to be developed at significantly lower cost [4].

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